

Supplementary Figure 3. Reference Checklist Levit et al. (2018).		
Title Page	Title	Identify key issues/topic under consideration.
	Author Note	Acknowledge funding sources or contributors. Acknowledge conflicts of interest, if any.
Abstract		State the problem/question/objectives under investigation. Indicate the study design, including types of participants or data sources, analytic strategy, main results/findings, and main implications/significance.
		Identify five keywords.
Introduction	Description of Research Problem or Question	Frame the problem or question and its context. Review, critique, and synthesize the applicable literature to identify key issues/debates/ theoretical frameworks in the relevant literature to clarify barriers, knowledge gaps, or practical needs.
	Study Objectives/Aims/Research Goals	State the purpose(s)/goal(s)/aim(s) of the study. State the target audience, if specific. Provide the rationale for fit of design used to investigate this purpose/goal (e.g., theory building, explanatory, developing understanding, social action, description, highlighting social practices). Describe the approach to inquiry, if it illuminates the objectives and research rationale (e.g., descriptive, interpretive, feminist, psychoanalytic, postpositivist, critical, postmodern, constructivist, or pragmatic approaches).
Researcher Description		Describe the researchers' backgrounds in approaching the study, emphasizing their prior understandings of the phenomena under study (e.g., interviewers, analysts, or research team). Describe how prior understandings of the phenomena under study were managed and/or influenced the research (e.g., enhancing, limiting, or structuring data collection and analysis).
Method	Research Design Overview	Summarize the research design, including data-collection strategies, data-analytic strategies, and, if illuminating, approaches to inquiry (e.g., descriptive, interpretive, feminist, psychoanalytic, postpositivist, critical, postmodern, constructivist, or pragmatic approaches). Provide the rationale for the design selected.
	Data Sources & Recruitment Process	Provide the numbers of participants/documents/events analyzed. Indicate software, if used.
	Participant Selection	Describe the participants/data source selection process (e.g., purposive sampling methods, such as maximum variation; convenience sampling methods, such as snowball selection; theoretical sampling; diversity sampling) and inclusion/exclusion criteria. Provide the general context for the study (when data were collected, sites of data collection).
	Data Collection/Identification Procedures	State the form of data collected (e.g., interviews, questionnaires, media, observation). Describe the origins or evolution of the data-collection protocol. Describe questions asked in data collection: content of central questions, form of questions (e.g., open vs. closed).
	Recording and Data Transformation	Describe the methods and procedures used and for what purpose/goal.
	Data-Analytic Strategies	Explicate in detail the process of analysis, including some discussion of the procedures (e.g., coding, thematic analysis) following a principle of transparency. Identify whether coding categories emerged from the analyses or were developed a priori. Identify units of analysis (e.g., entire transcript, unit, text) and how units were formed, if applicable.
	Methodological Integrity	Demonstrate that the claims made from the analysis are warranted and have produced findings with methodological integrity. The procedures that support methodological integrity (i.e., fidelity and utility) typically are described across the relevant sections of a paper, but they could be addressed in a separate section when elaboration or emphasis would be helpful. Issues of methodological integrity include the following: Assess the adequacy of the data in terms of its ability to capture forms of diversity most relevant to the question, research goals, and inquiry approach. Describe how the researchers' perspectives were managed in both the data collection and analysis (e.g., to limit their effect on the data collection, to structure the analysis) Demonstrate that the contributions are insightful and meaningful (e.g., in relation to the current literature and the study goal). Provide relevant contextual information for findings (e.g., setting of study, information about participants, interview question asked is presented before excerpt as needed). Demonstrate consistency with regard to the analytic processes (e.g., analysts may use demonstrations of analyses to support consistency, describe their development of a stable perspective, interrater reliability, consensus) or describe responses to inconsistencies, as relevant (e.g., coders switching midway through analysis, an interruption in the analytic process). If alterations in methodological integrity were made for ethical reasons, explicate those reasons and the adjustments made. data displays/matrices in-depth thick description, case examples, or illustrations
Findings/Results		Describe research findings (e.g., themes, categories, narratives) and the meaning and understandings that the researcher has derived from the data analysis. Demonstrate the analytic process of reaching findings (e.g., quotes, excerpts of data). Present research findings in a way that is compatible with the study design.
Discussion		Describe the central contributions and their significance in advancing disciplinary understandings. Describe the types of contributions made by findings (e.g., challenging, elaborating on, and supporting prior research or theory in the literature describing the relevance) and how findings can be best utilized. Identify the study's strengths and limitations (e.g., consider how the quality, source, or types of the data or the analytic processes might support or weaken its methodological integrity). Consider the implications for future research, policy, or practice.

Supplementary Figure 3. Reference Checklist from Levit et al. (2018). This table captures the elements that guide this protocol's organization.